

Determining antimicrobial susceptibility and antimicrobial resistance mechanisms in the clinical laboratory: where are we and where are we heading?

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Summary

Since the discovery of penicillin, almost a century ago, the battle against resistant microbes has been fierce but uneven. Microbes have been proven quite adaptable and have developed many different antimicrobial resistance (AMR) mechanisms to evade antibiotics. These AMR mechanisms mainly regulate cephalosporin and carbapenem resistance for Gram-negative bacteria, methicillin resistance for *Staphylococcus aureus* and vancomycin resistance for Enterococci. Greece is endemic for most known multi-drug resistant organisms (MDRO) that often cause community and hospital-acquired infections, perplexing treatment, increasing length of stay in the hospital and relevant costs, and increasing morbidity and mortality. Detection and treatment of such infections in a timely and effective way is imperative. For the past few decades, scientists from dif-

ferent scientific fields have been developing technologies and methods to assist the early and reliable detection of AMR to optimize not only treatment but also infection control practices in an effort to restrain it. This review focuses on current practices to detect AMR and the corresponding resistance mechanisms. From the well-established classic diffusion antibiogram to the rapid automated tools that provide susceptibility profiles of bacteria within a few hours, and from the time-consuming phenotypic AMR detection methods to rapid molecular AMR mechanism detection directly from the sample, Microbiology has come a long way. Most microbiological laboratories are currently using a combination of phenotypic and molecular methods for AMR detection, in an effort to make the best out of both. Integrating novel technologies into the laboratory routine workflow has its challenges, with the financial burden being one of the most significant. However, if the progress in the field of Microbiology since the emergence of the first resistant microbe until now is any indication, the future holds many more adventures and scientific breakthroughs in the fight against AMR.

Key words

Antimicrobial susceptibility; antimicrobial resistance mechanisms; phenotypic resistance detection; molecular resistance detection

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The road so far

Microbes have been living on Earth long before humans came into the picture. They have left their small carbon footprints in rocks and stromatolites dating back approximately 3.5 billion years. All this extra time has worked on their benefit, rendering them smarter, fitter, and more adaptable through countless evolutionary events. After the discovery of penicillin by Sir Alexander Fleming in 1928, the medical community, and along with it all of humanity, thought that triumph over microbes and subsequently the end of microbial infections was near. Unfortunately, it went down the exact opposite way. A few years later, in 1940, Abraham and Chain reported an *Escherichia coli* strain that produced penicillinase, followed by reports of resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* strains.^{1,2} For every new antibiotic agent ever since, bacteria would adapt and develop a corresponding resistance mechanism.

The World Health Organisation has included antimicrobial resistance (AMR) in the three most important public health threats of the 21st century.³

Sharing the same ecological niche with other organisms that naturally produced antibiotic compounds, led to species exhibiting a plethora of different intrinsic resistance profiles.⁴ However, intrinsic resistance does not substantially add to the AMR problem. When observing the AMR issue through the clinical lens, acquired resistance, i.e. resistance to antibiotics to which they were previously susceptible, is of importance. Acquired resistance can be a result of either a series of genetic mutating events altering the way a bacterium responds to the antibiotic compound, or by obtaining genetic material associated with resistance through horizontal transfer. Genetic mutations can lead to alterations in the antimicrobial target, decrease in the drug uptake, activation of efflux mechanisms extruding the compound, or alter-

ations in important metabolic pathways.⁵ Genetic horizontal transfer is the result of transformation, transduction, and conjugation. Clinically relevant bacteria often acquire resistance through conjugation, using genetic mobile elements, namely plasmids, transposons and intergrons.⁶

Main mechanisms of resistance in *Enterobacterales* are the production of extended spectrum β -lactamases (ESBL) rendering them resistant to third generation cephalosporins, and carbapenemase production leading to carbapenem resistance. Carbapenemases are classified in four classes according to Ambler, the most frequently used classification system. Clinically important strains produce *Klebsiella pneumoniae*-carbapenemases (KPC) (class A), metallo- β -lactamases VIM and NDM (class B) and OXA-48 (class D).⁷ Resistance to carbapenems in *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* is mediated by OprD loss and class B carbapenemase production such as VIM, IMP or NDM, while *Acinetobacter baumannii* produces non-OXA-48 class D carbapenemases.^{8,9} The main mechanism for resistance to β -lactams in *S. aureus* is penicillin-binding protein production (PBP) resulting in low β -lactam affinity. Genes *mecA* and *mecC* code for production of PBP2a and PBP2, leading to methicillin resistance (MRSA).¹⁰ Lastly, VanA or VanB ligases lead to reduced glycopeptides binding resulting in vancomycin resistance (VRE).¹¹

Greece is endemic for most known multi-drug-resistant organisms (MDRO). According to the latest antimicrobial resistance report,¹² *Escherichia coli* strains reported from Greece are resistant to third generation cephalosporins at a percentage of 21.9%, to fluoroquinolones 32.7% and to aminoglycosides 18.7%. Reported *K. pneumoniae* isolates are resistant to third generation cephalosporins at a percentage of 74.5%, to carbapenems 66.3%, to fluoroquinolones 74.4% and 61.0% to aminoglycosides. Furthermore, 35.7% and 28.6% of *P. aeruginosa* strains are resistant to carbapenems and aminoglycosides, respectively, while 94.6% of *A. baumannii* strains are carbapenem-resistant. In regard to Gram-positive bacteria, 40.2% of reported *S. aureus* strains are resistant to methicillin and 41.8% of *Enterococcus faecium* strains are resistant to vancomycin.¹²

Pathogens exhibiting resistance to different antibiotic compounds often cause community and hospital-acquired infections, perplexing treatment, increasing length of stay in the hospital and relevant costs and increasing morbidity and mortality.¹³ It is imperative to detect and treat these infections in a timely and effective way. For the past few decades, scientists from different scientific fields have been developing technologies and methods to assist the early and reliable detection of AMR to optimize not only

treatment but also infection control practices in an effort to restrain it.

Where are we

Antimicrobial susceptibility testing (Antibiogram)

1. Classic tools

Antimicrobial susceptibility testing (AST) is the first step to determine the resistance profile of a strain. Classical methods include agar and broth macro- and micro- dilution to determine minimal inhibitory concentration (MIC) of antibiotic agents.¹⁴ The broth microdilution method has been used extensively and is currently the basis of both the Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute (CLSI) and European Committee on Antimicrobial Susceptibility Testing (EUCAST) standard methodologies. MIC can also be determined by using ETEST[®], an antibiotic gradient method that combines agar dilution and disk diffusion principles. Disk diffusion as described by Kirby and Bauer in 1956, is easy to perform, and microbiological laboratories around the world have incorporated this method in their clinical routine workflows, for decades.^{15,16} Disk diffusion is well established and standardised, easy, simple, practical and of low cost. Breakpoints for all relevant clinical and emerging bacteria for disk diffusion, broth microdilution and ETEST[®] methods are available according to both, CLSI and EUCAST.¹⁷ Furthermore, during the past two decades, a variety of chromogenic agar media for detection of resistant strains, including ESBL and carbapenemases production in Gram-negative bacteria, MRSA and VRE, has been developed.^{18,19} Lastly, colorimetric tests for the detection of carbapenemase production, that utilize pH changes indicative of growth of resistant bacteria have been developed in recent years.²⁰

2. Automated tools

The introduction of automated devices for AST has changed the landscape of the daily microbiological routine. These devices perform broth-based microdilution testing utilising wells with broth with increasing concentrations of various antibiotics and continuous monitoring of microbial growth and turbidity to provide MIC. They are efficient, easy to use, of relatively low cost and provide results for both identification and AST fast, significantly reducing the turnaround time compared to the classical methods. The three most widely used Food and Drug Administration (FDA)-approved automated systems are VITEK 2 (bioMérieux, France), Phoenix system (BD Diagnostic Systems, Baltimore, MD, USA) and MicroScan Walkaway (Dade-Behring MicroScan, Deerfield, IL, USA).²¹

3. Rapid tools

Increasing pressure for identification and susceptibility testing of microbes causing life-threatening infections, such as blood stream infections, has led to the development of rapid AST systems. The use of these rapid systems can reduce even further the turnaround time, with identification and AST results in up to 4-6 hours. Technologies behind rapid systems include darkfield microscopy, real imaging, cell sorting, flow cytometry, microfluidics, and bioluminescence.²² Three rapid AST systems have been more extensively described and evaluated in the existing literature. QMAC-dRAST system (QuantaMatrix, Seoul, South Korea), not FDA-approved yet (application submitted in November 2019), utilizes time-lapse microscopic imagery of bacterial colony formation in agarose to determine AST directly from positive blood cultures in as low as 4 hours. In a study from Switzerland that included 130 *Enterobacteriales*, 20 non-fermentative Gram-negative bacteria, 69 staphylococci and 31 enterococci, the overall categorical agreement, compared to BD Phoenix™ M50, was 95.1%, 91.2%, 93.4% and 94.5%, respectively. The median time to result was 6.7 hours and observed very major errors (classification of a resistant strain as susceptible) were below 4%, with the exception of staphylococci (7%).²³ Specific Reveal™ (bioMérieux, France) is a Breakthrough Device Designation – FDA-approved device for rapid AST results, directly from positive blood cultures with a turnaround time of approximately 5.5 hours. The device uses small molecule sensors to detect the volatiles released by microbes as they grow, to quantify antibiotic efficacy. In a recent American study, Specific Reveal showed 96.3% and 96.2% categorical agreement, when compared to Sensititre and Vitek 2, respectively. Very major errors were observed at a percentage of 1.3%.²⁴ Accelerate Pheno® system (Accelerate Diagnostics, USA) is an FDA approved method for microbial identification and AST in 2 and 7 hours, respectively. The system uses gel electrofiltration and fluorescence *in situ* hybridization for identification of Gram-negative bacteria and automated microscopy for bacterial growth rates for AST. In recent studies, Accelerate Pheno has shown high categorical agreement and low percentage of very major errors when compared to different methods, including MALDI-TOF and Vitek 2^{25,26} and is currently under clinical evaluation.

AMR detection

1. Phenotypic tools

Phenotypic tests for detection of AMR mechanisms from microbial colonies have been widely used in mi-

crobiological laboratories. Double Disk Synergy Test is used to detect ESBL production in Gram-negative bacteria, interpreting inhibition zone diameter differences for cephalosporins with and without β -lactamase inhibitors such as clavulanate.²⁷ Several tests have been developed to detect carbapenemase production, some of which can also differentiate between different carbapenemase classes. The use of the Modified Hodge Test for carbapenemase detection is no longer recommended by the CLSI due to false positive results for ESBL and AmpC producers, and false negative results for metallo- β -lactamase producers.²⁸ The Carbapenem Inactivation Method (CIM) detects carbapenemase production by assessing growth or no growth of a susceptible *E. coli* strain around a meropenem disk previously immersed in a suspension of the microbe under investigation. A modified version of CIM, exhibiting high sensitivity and specificity, is recommended by the CLSI.²⁹ The Combination Meropenem Disk Test is based on the inhibiting abilities of boronic acid for KPC carbapenemase and EDTA for metallo- β -lactamase to differentiate between different carbapenemase classes.³⁰

CLSI guidelines recommend Carba NP, CIM, and/or a molecular assay for carbapenemase detection when suspected, namely when MIC for imipenem and meropenem is below 4 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ and below 2 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ for ertapenem. Screening cut-off values for carbapenemase production according to EUCAST for meropenem and ertapenem MIC is 0.125 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ and 28 and 25 mm, respectively. Further investigation is recommended by using a phenotypic method such as a combined disk test, a colorimetric assay, or a lateral flow immunoassay (LFIA). Choosing the appropriate method for carbapenemase production depends mostly on the available resources and the local epidemiology of resistant microorganisms. Greece is endemic for most carbapenemases-producing *Enterobacteriales*, hence laboratories use a combined disk test, such as the Combination Meropenem Disk Test, that confirms carbapenemase production and at the same time differentiates between different classes.

The main disadvantage of the growth-based methods is the need for an incubation of up to 24 hours. Colorimetric tests are based on biochemical or electrochemical reactions that provide result in a few hours. Carba NP test and its variants utilize incubating imipenem with the strain under investigation and a pH indicator. Hydrolysis of imipenem is indicated by the change of colour when the pH changes.³¹ Sensitivity and specificity are high for most carbapenemases produced by *Enterobacteriales*, with the exception of OXA-48. Modified versions of the colorimetric tests have shown improved detection for all carba-

penemases including enzymes produced by non-fermentative Gram-negative bacteria.³² LFIA for detection of carbapenemase production can provide definitive results directly from grown colonies in as little as 15 minutes. Multiplex LFIA exhibit high sensitivity and specificity for all clinically relevant carbapenemases, namely KPC, metallo- β -lactamases and OXA-48 produced by both *Enterobacteriales* and non-fermenters.³³ Local epidemiology and the fact that LFIA cannot detect newly emerging carbapenemases or rare ones should be taken under account. Even though LFIA is a simple to use and rapid method, the relatively high cost is an important factor of consideration when integrating the method in routine laboratory workflow.

Resistance to methicillin for *Staphylococcus aureus* strains can be determined using a disk of cefoxitin as recommended by both the CLSI and EUCAST, with a sensitivity of 97.2% and specificity of 100%, or by any AST method. Resistance to methicillin can also be determined by detecting the PBP2a protein directly on isolated colonies, using latex agglutination (Oxoid, Thermo Fisher Scientific Inc., Lenexa, KS, USA) and an immunochromatographic method (Alere, Abbott Diagnostics, Abbott Park, IL, USA). Both methods exhibit high sensitivity but relatively low specificity, due to inability to detect methicillin resistance mediated by the *mecC* gene.³⁴ Different AST methods either based on inhibition zones or MIC, can be used to determine resistance to vancomycin for enterococci. Correct species identification is imperative to avoid reporting strains intrinsically resistant to vancomycin, such as *Enterococcus gallinarum* and *E. casseliflavus*. Resistance to both vancomycin and teicoplanin indicate the presence of *vanA* gene while resistance only to vancomycin the presence of *vanB* gene.³⁵ LFIA and immunoassays have been proposed and tested for the detection of VRE in clinical and food samples. The NG-Test *VanA* and *VanB* (NG Biotech, France) have shown excellent sensitivity and specificity.^{36,37} However, determining the presence of *VanA* or *VanB* using LFIA or immunoassays significantly increases the cost, when resistance to vancomycin can be detected by classic cheaper methods like disk diffusion, while not adding to the infection control practices.

2. Molecular tools

Several molecular methods have been used during the past few decades for the detection of resistance genes associated with all known AMR mechanisms, like pulsed-field gel electrophoresis (PFGE), amplified fragment length polymorphism (AFLP), arbitrarily primed PCR (e.g. RAPD) and multilocus sequence typing (MLST). Whole genome sequence (WGS) has slowly replaced these methods, providing an abundance of

information not only in regard to AMR genes, but also to phylogenetic relatedness and bacterial typing.³⁸ However, WGS has certain disadvantages, like high costs, and requiring special equipment and trained personnel, rendering integrating the method into laboratory routine workflows difficult.³⁹

Genotypic AMR detection methods provide quick and reliable results, either from bacterial colonies or directly from clinical samples, without time-consuming incubation. Such methods may detect a single AMR mechanism or use syndromic panels to detect multiple AMR mechanisms.⁴⁰ Several FDA-approved systems have already been integrated into routine microbiological workflows and evaluated in clinical settings, in recent years.⁴¹

The GeneXpert® system (Cepheid, USA), is an automated platform that provides a variety of assays for AMR detection using real-time polymerase chain reaction (PCR). The instrument can detect the presence of genes associated with all clinically relevant carbapenemases (*bla_{IMP}*, *bla_{NDM}*, *bla_{VIM}*, *bla_{OXA-48}*, *bla_{KPC}*) produced by *Enterobacteriales* and *P. aeruginosa* from bacterial colonies, using the CARBA-R assay. The MRSA/SA SSTI and Xpert MRSA/SA, MRSA Nasal Complete assays can detect *mecA*, *SCC_{mec}* and *attB* junction for MRSA, from skin and soft tissue and nasal swabs, respectively. In addition, the Xpert *vanA* and Xpert Carba-R assays can detect *vanA* VRE and carbapenemase genes from *Enterobacteriales*, *A. baumannii* and *P. aeruginosa*, directly from rectal swabs. An Xpert MRSA/SA BC assay has been developed for MRSA detection directly from positive blood cultures.⁴²

The VERIGENE® II System (Luminex, USA) is a molecular diagnostic platform that performs both targeted and multiplex testing on a single sample. The Staphylococcus Blood Culture (BC-S) Nucleic Acid assay detects the *mecA* gene for MRSA and the *mecA*, *vanA*, *vanB* genes for MRSA and enterococci, directly from positive blood cultures.⁴³ In addition, the BC-GN assay detects carbapenemase related genes (*bla_{CTX-M}*, *bla_{IMP}*, *bla_{NDM}*, *bla_{VIM}*, *bla_{OXA}*, *bla_{KPC}*) for Gram-negative bacteria in positive blood cultures.

The FilmArray (BioFire Diagnostics, USA) platform is a sample-to-answer multiplex PCR syndromic system for the identification of relevant microbial pathogens and detection of AMR genes. The BioFire PN panel detects clinically relevant microbes and associated AMR genes from lower tract respiratory specimens. In addition, the BioFire BCID2 panel detects a wide variety of pathogens from positive blood cultures and AMR genes associated with carbapenemase and ESBL production for Gram-negative bacteria, methicillin resistance for *S. aureus* and vancomycin resistance for enterococci.⁴⁴

3. Proteomic tools

Matrix-assisted laser desorption/ionization time-of-flight mass spectrometry (MALDI-TOF MS) has been extensively used in recent years for the rapid identification of microorganisms. The method has also been used to detect specific resistance mechanisms by quantifying bacterial enzyme activity towards antibiotics or direct detection of genes associated with antibiotic resistance.⁴⁵ However, the application of the method in practice is debatable since MIC determination is not possible. Furthermore, detection of resistance gene presence does not necessarily translate to resistance to antibiotics.

Where are we heading

Road bumps ahead and future perspectives

Most microbiological laboratories are currently using a combination of phenotypic and molecular methods for AMR detection, in an effort to make the best out of both. Phenotypic detection often requires prolonged turnaround time but is of lower cost, while molecular methods are fast, yet expensive. Patients might benefit from laboratory workflows that prioritize molecular detection in clinical specimens with indication of invasive life-threatening infection. For example, using a combination of a rapid identification system such as MALDI-TOF, after rapid incubation of a positive blood culture, with a rapid AST platform, followed by phenotypic AMR detection via LFIA, could yield results in only a few hours. In addition, for critically ill patients or patients with known MDRO risk factors, with a positive blood culture, using a sample-to-answer syndromic platform, can provide valuable information in as fast as one hour. Furthermore, rapid detection or no detection of any AMR mechanism can optimize antibiotic stewardship efforts.

Even though Microbiology has come a long way since the detection of the first resistant microbe, there are still some obstacles we need to overcome. Integrating rapid phenotypic and molecular methods for AMR detection in the daily laboratory routine requires keeping up with innovative and cutting-edge technologies, special equipment, trained personnel, and efficiently utilize and communicate the relevant information and data to clinicians, in order to optimize clinical practices. More importantly, these methods need to be integrated in a financially sustainable way, especially in MDRO endemic environments like Greece, where the high number of isolated MDRO can substantially increase the costs.

There are currently many promising technologies

in the field of AMR detection, at the stage of proof of concept. These include microfluidics with automated time-lapse photomicrography, measuring optical density and the scattered intensity by forward laser light scattering, single-cell morphological analysis, detection of volatile organic compounds associated with microbial metabolism, and cultivation and semi quantitative smartphone-based visual analysis of nucleic acid products.⁴⁶

Artificial intelligence (AI) is a field that combines computer science and robust datasets, to enable problem-solving. Machine-learning is a branch of AI that utilizes data and algorithms to imitate the way the human brain learns and processes information to improve performance. AI has already been tested through different angles, in order to determine the different approaches that can be used regarding AMR detection and management. These approaches include the prediction of AMR by a combination of flow cytometry and machine learning and a combination of infrared spectroscopy with artificial neural network.⁴⁷ In addition, AI can analyse and manage shotgun or metagenomic DNA sequences for the prediction of AMR. Furthermore, machine learning models have shown potential for diagnosing sepsis based on parameters such as clinical signs, biochemical factors and biomarkers, and ultimately support the optimization of antibiotic strategies for sepsis. However, integrating AI for AMR detection in clinical laboratories poses some significant challenges. In addition to the extensive training needed to use AI programs and interpret the results, obtaining the necessary big data to export clinically relevant conclusions is expensive and time consuming. Data quality, also significantly affects AI performance. Lastly, when it comes to AMR mechanisms for less common microorganisms or isolated from unusual environments, it is challenging to develop effective machine-learning models.^{48,49}

Conclusions

This review demonstrates the abundance of methods at our disposal when it comes to battling AMR. The susceptibility profile of a microorganism can be determined by the inhibition zones of the simple disk diffusion method, by the MIC provided by BMD, ETEST© and automated tools or even directly from positive blood cultures in a matter of a few hours. In addition, AMR mechanisms can be detected using phenotypic disk tests, immunoassays, LFIA and more elaborate molecular methods. Many more principles and methods are currently being developed and tested to that end.

Undoubtedly, evolution of AMR poses various challenges and often complicates the development of efficient diagnostic tools, the determination of optimal treatment and the implementation of appropriate infection control practices. However, if the progress in the field of Microbiology since the emergence of the first resistant microbe until now is any indication, the future holds many more adventures and scientific breakthroughs in the fight against AMR.

Conflict of interest

The author declares no conflict of interest.

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Περίληψη

Μεθοδολογίες προσδιορισμού της αντιμικροβιακής ευαισθησίας και των μηχανισμών μικροβιακής αντοχής στο κλινικό εργαστήριο: πού βρισκόμαστε και πού οδεύουμε;

Νεκταρία Ρεκλείτη

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Από την ανακάλυψη της πενικιλίνης, περίπου έναν αιώνα πριν μέχρι σήμερα, η μάχη εναντίον των μικροβίων έχει υπάρξει σφοδρή αλλά και άνιση. Τα μικρόβια έχουν αποδειχθεί εξαιρετικά ευπροσάρμοστα αναπτύσσοντας πολλούς διαφορετικούς μηχανισμούς αντοχής απέναντι στα αντιβιοτικά. Οι κυριότεροι μηχανισμοί αντοχής αφορούν την αδρανοποίηση των κεφαλοσπορινών και των καρβαπενεμών για τα Gram αρνητικά βακτήρια, την αντοχή στην μεθικιλίνη για τον *Staphylococcus aureus* και την αντοχή στην βανκομυκίνη για τους εντεροκόκκους. Η Ελλάδα είναι ενδημική για τα περισσότερα πολυανθεκτικά μικρόβια τα οποία προκαλούν ενδοноσοκομειακές λοιμώξεις, αλλά και λοιμώξεις της κοινότητας που περιπλέκουν την θεραπεία των ασθενών, επιμηκύνουν την παραμονή τους στο νοσοκομείο, αυξάνουν το κόστος νοσηλείας και εμφανίζουν υψηλή νοσηρότητα και θνητότητα. Η ανίχνευση και θεραπεία των λοιμώξεων από πολυανθεκτικά μικρόβια με τρόπο αξιόπιστο και γρήγορο είναι ιδιαίτερα σημαντική. Τις τελευταίες δεκαετίες επιστήμονες από διαφορετικά πεδία έχουν αναπτύξει νέες τεχνολογίες και μεθόδους, με σκοπό να βελτιστοποιηθεί τόσο η θεραπευτική αντιμετώπιση όσο και οι πρακτικές ελέγχου λοιμώξεων. Με την παρούσα μελέτη γίνεται μια ανασκόπηση των μεθόδων ανίχνευσης αντιμικροβιακής αντοχής και των μηχανισμών της. Από το κλασικό αντιβιογράμμα διάχυσης δίσκων στα γρήγορα συστήματα καθορισμού προφίλ ευαισθησίας μέσα σε λίγες μόνο ώρες, και από τις πολύωρες φαινοτυπικές μεθόδους ανίχνευσης αντοχής μέχρι τα γρήγορα μοριακά πάνελ ανίχνευσης μηχανισμού αντοχής απευθείας από το δείγμα, η Μικροβιολογία έχει κάνει άλματα. Τα περισσότερα μικροβιολογικά εργαστήρια χρησιμοποιούν έναν συνδυασμό των κλασικών και των νεότερων μοριακών μεθόδων για την ανίχνευση του μηχανισμού αντοχής, καθώς η αποκλειστική εφαρμογή μοριακών μεθόδων εμφανίζει ακόμη αρκετές προκλήσεις, με μια από τις κυριότερες την οικονομική επιβάρυνση. Ωστόσο, η αλματώδης πρόοδος της Μικροβιολογίας από την εμφάνιση του πρώτου ανθεκτικού μικροβίου μέχρι και σήμερα, αποτελεί ελπιδοφόρο οίονό για το μέλλον και τις συναρπαστικές ανακαλύψεις που θα φέρει.

Λέξεις κλειδιά

Αντιβιογράμμα, μηχανισμός αντοχής στα αντιβιοτικά, φαινοτυπική ανίχνευση αντιμικροβιακής αντοχής, μοριακή ανίχνευση αντιμικροβιακής αντοχής

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